

Vinyl Fluorides: Competent Olefinic Counterparts in the Intramolecular Pauson–Khand Reaction

Raquel Romá, Natalia Mateu,[‡] Inés López,[‡] Mercedes Medio-Simon,[‡] Santos Fustero,^{*,‡,‡} and Pablo Barrio

[†]Departamento de Química Orgánica, Universidad de Valencia, E-46100 Burjassot, Spain

[‡]Laboratorio de Moléculas Orgánicas, Centro de Investigación Príncipe Felipe, E-46012 Valencia, Spain

ABSTRACT: Despite the great advances achieved in the Pauson–Khand reaction and the ever-increasing demand for fluorinated compounds, the use of vinyl fluorides as olefinic counterparts in the above-mentioned transformation had been completely overlooked. Herein, we describe, for the first time, the intramolecular Pauson–Khand reaction of enynes containing a vinyl fluoride moiety.

The ever-increasing demand for organofluorine compounds by key industrial fields such as the pharmaceutical, agrochemical, or materials is unquestionable.¹ In recent years, following a general trend in drug discovery referred to as escape from flatland, the synthesis of new molecular entities bearing a fluorine atom or a fluorinated motif directly attached to an sp³ carbon atom has received renewed impetus.² Within this trend, the installation of a fluorine atom in a quaternary stereocenter is of paramount importance.³ On the other hand, the Pauson–Khand reaction (PKR) has arguably become the methodology of choice for the preparation of the cyclopentenone core, especially for the synthesis of bicyclic scaffolds by means of the intramolecular version.⁴ In our continuous efforts to construct functionalized monofluorinated scaffolds, we envisioned the use of vinyl fluorides as olefinic counterparts in this emblematic transformation (Scheme 1, equation a).⁵ While we and others have achieved significant advances in broadening the scope with regard to the substitution at the triple bond (Scheme 1, eq b),⁶ we were astonished to find that the use of not only fluoro olefins but also heteroatom-substituted olefins had been overlooked in this area (Scheme 1, eq a).^{7,8}

Scheme 1. Pauson–Khand Reactions with Heteroatom-Substituted Olefins and Alkynes

Variability at the olefinic counterpart

X = H, C No example with X = heteroatom

This work: X = F

Variability at the acetylenic counterpart

Previous work: X = CF₃, Bpin, SiR₃

In view of the increasing availability of fluorinated building blocks and fluorination methodologies,⁹ we set out to tackle this striking synthetic lack. A literature search revealed that the required fluorinated 1,*n*-enynes were hitherto unknown.¹⁰ Our first challenge, then, was the synthesis of an appropriate model substrate (Scheme 2). Recently, Hammond disclosed the Markovnikov hydrofluorination of terminal alkynes using HF·DMPU and gold catalysis.¹¹ In

that report, product 2a caught our attention since it could be transformed into model substrate 3a just by propargylation of the fluoroallylmalonate intermediate 2a. Hence, starting from commercially available diethyl propargyl malonate 1a, 3a was obtained in two steps in good overall yield (Scheme 2).

Scheme 2. Synthesis of Model Substrate 3a

This model substrate was then used to assess suitable reaction conditions for the unprecedented fluoro Pauson–Khand reaction (Table 1). We started the optimization using the reaction conditions that had already proved successful by our group in several structurally diverse scenarios, namely, NMO (10 equiv, CH₂Cl₂, rt) (Scheme 3).^{6b,12} Under these reaction conditions, however, the only defined species formed was elimination product 4a. This substructure was reported to be formed by the palladium-catalyzed carbonylation of diynes 6 (Scheme 3).¹³ Since *N*-methyl morpholine is the only base present in the reaction medium and the reaction conditions are very mild, the elimination of HF from 4a to form 6 or 6' seemed unlikely.^{13b} We anticipated that 4a may be formed instead by elimination of HF from 5a (Scheme 3).¹⁴ The antiaromatic character of the corresponding cyclopentadienone would account for the complete regioselectivity observed in the elimination step. This possibility would mean that the fluoro-PKR takes place and that the desired product 5a could be afforded just by avoiding the elimination reaction.

Encouraged by this promising result, we decided to carry out an optimization of the reaction conditions avoiding the use of NMO as an oxidant, rather looking for an oxidizing promoter that would render a reduced neutral species. A pioneering study by Pauson showed that DMSO is also able to promote the PKR, albeit under somewhat more energetic reaction conditions.¹⁵ To our delight, 5a was the major product when using DMSO as the promoter, regardless of the reaction conditions (equivalents of DMSO, solvent, temperature) (Table 1). The conditions shown in entry 3 were selected as optimal and used to subsequently determine the

scope of the reaction (see below).

Table 1. Optimization of Reaction Conditions

entry	promoter	n	solvent	t ($^\circ\text{C}$)	t (h)	4a (%)	5a (%)
1	NMO	10	CH_2Cl_2	rt	4	41	–
2	NMO	10	DCE	50	4	60	–
3	DMSO	1	CH_2Cl_2	40	4	–	70
4	DMSO	2	CH_2Cl_2	40	4	–	67
5	DMSO	3	CH_2Cl_2	40	4	–	71
6	DMSO	3	toluene	60	18	–	68

Before disclosing our findings regarding the scope of the reaction, a brief description of the synthesis of the starting materials will be outlined (Scheme 4). Most malonate derivatives **3** were synthesized by an analogous route to that depicted in Scheme 2, namely hydrofluorination of the corresponding propargyl malonate **1**, followed by propargylation of intermediates **2** with suitable propargyl bromides **7** (Scheme 4). In addition, the availability of fluoroallyl alcohol allowed us to envision an alternative *metal-free* approach that, in addition, was also amenable for the preparation of heteroatom tethered enyne derivatives **3i–s** (Scheme 4). Direct propargyl ether formation by Williamson's synthesis afforded **3i,j** in moderate yields. For the synthesis of chiral ether **3k**, an alternative FeCl_3 -catalyzed methodology was required.¹⁶ Mesylate **8**, first described by Mykhailiuk,¹⁷ allowed the preparation of *N*- and *S*-tethered substrates **3l,m,o,p**. Moreover, this approach proved to be the only alternative for the preparation of malononitrile-derived analog **3n**, since propargyl malononitrile was reluctant to Hammond's hydrofluorination conditions. In order to showcase the applicability of our methodology for the synthesis of complex scaffolds of pharmaceutical interest,¹⁸ isatin derivatives **3q,r** were prepared by an analogous strategy (Scheme 4). Furthermore, a phenylalanine residue was attached to the triple bond of the enyne scaffold **3s** (Scheme 4).

Scheme 4. Synthesis of Starting Materials **3a–s**

conditions optimized for **3a** (Scheme 5). First, as expected, a change in the ester substituent at the malonate moiety had no noticeable impact on the reaction efficiency (Scheme 5, **5a,b**). Similarly, moderate to good yields were obtained for derivatives bearing aryl substituents at the propargyl moiety regardless of their electronic nature (Scheme 5, **5c–e**). On the other hand, while alkyl-substituted derivative **5g** was afforded in the same chemical yield range as the aryl substituted ones, a significant drop in reactivity was obtained for the corresponding TMS-substituted derivative **5f**. This diminished reactivity translated in both a poor chemical yield and an extended reaction time.¹⁹ Unfortunately, the use of homopropargyl derivative **3h** did not allow the preparation of the corresponding 6,5-bicyclic system. Regarding the use of tethering functionalities other than malonates, while heteroatomic moieties such as ethers or tosylamine were well-tolerated (Scheme 5, **5i–m**), the use of a sulfur-based tether in **3o** and **3p** was unsuccessful.²⁰ Noteworthy, the use of chiral ether **3k** afforded the corresponding product **5k** in moderate yield and complete diastereoselectivity (Scheme 5).²¹ On the other hand, elimination product **4n** was exclusively obtained when using malononitrile as the spacer, under a variety of reaction conditions. To our delight, isatin derivatives **3q,r** afforded the corresponding spirocyclic derivatives **5q,r** as single diastereoisomers, albeit in low yields (Scheme 5).²¹ It is worth noting that the presence of a quaternary stereocenter in the tether enabled the formation of the hitherto reluctant 6,5 bicyclic system, presumably due to the Thorpe–Ingold effect. We were also delighted to achieve the formation of amino acid derivative **5s**, in moderate yield (Scheme 5).

Scheme 5. Scope and Limitations

With this small library of substrates **3a–s** in hand, we set out to explore the scope and limitations of the PKR reaction

^a**5b** was prepared in a gram scale procedure (×10, 70%). ^b18 h at 40 °C. ^cDirect PKR product not observed.

As commented in the introduction, neither fluoro olefins nor other vinyl halides have been used as olefinic counterparts in enynes for the intramolecular PKR. Intrigued by this fact, and with the aim of extending the scope of this transformation, we set out to explore the use of the corresponding chloro- and bromo-derivatives **10a,b**. The commercial availability of the corresponding 2,3-dihalopropene derivatives **9a,b** resulted in a straightforward one-step synthesis from dimethyl propargyl malonate **1b** (Scheme 6).

Scheme 6. Synthesis of Chloro and Bromo Analogs

Disappointingly, under various reaction conditions the corresponding PKR products were not observed in the crude reaction mixtures. By using the conditions optimized for the fluorinated analogs **3**, the major isolated product was the dimeric species **11** (Scheme 7). It is noteworthy that **11** was isolated as a single regio- and diastereoisomer. Although the desired product could not be isolated, the presence of the cyclopentenone subunit in the final product allowed the assumption that PKR products **12a,b** had indeed been formed and then transformed into the observed final product. The formation of this unexpected product may be explained by the inherent diminished strength of the C–X bond along the halide elements C–F > C–Cl > C–Br > C–I. These weakened C–X bonds along with the position of the halide at a tertiary carbon and the presence of stoichiometric amounts of cobalt, known to be prone to promote radical pathways,²² indicate that **11** was formed by dimerization of radical **I** arising from **12** (Scheme 7).

In conclusion, the synthesis of a new family of fluorinated enynes has been achieved for the first time, including malonates and heteroatoms as tethering units. These fluorinated building blocks have shown to be competent substrates for the intramolecular Pauson–Khand reaction, by using appropriate reaction conditions that preclude the inherent tendency of the obtained adducts to eliminate HF. Moreover, the unprecedented bicyclic cyclopentenones featuring a fluorine atom at a fully substituted bridgehead carbon would be difficult to access by current synthetic methodologies.²³ Finally, the strength of the C–F bond hampers the radical pathway observed for other halogen derivatives, showcasing the unique reactivity of organofluorine compounds. Further studies aimed at the development of a catalytic, ideally enantioselective, variant of this transformation are currently underway.²⁴ In addition, the versatility of 1,6-enynes as substrates for transition-metal-catalyzed transformations is also under study with our new fluorinated analogs.²⁵

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- (1) For books on organofluorine chemistry, see: (a) Hiyama, H. *Organofluorine Compounds: Chemistry and Applications*; Springer: Berlin, 2000. (b) Chambers, R. D.; Fluorine, R. D. *Organic Chemistry*; Blackwell Publishing Ltd.: Oxford, 2004. (c) Kirsch, P. *Modern Fluoroorganic Chemistry: Synthesis, Reactivity, Applications*; Wiley-VCH: Weinheim, 2004. (d) Uneyama, K. *Organofluorine Chemistry*; Blackwell Publishing Ltd.: Oxford, 2006.
- (2) (a) Lovering, F. Escape from Flatland 2: complexity and promiscuity. *MedChemComm* 2013, 4, 515. (b) Lovering, F.; Bikker, J.; Humblet, C. Escape from Flatland: Increasing Saturation as an Approach to Improving Clinical Success. *J. Med. Chem.* 2009, 52, 6752.
- (3) Zhu, Y.; Han, J.; Wang, J.; Shibata, N.; Sodeoka, M.; Soloshonok, V. A.; Coelho, J. A. S.; Toste, F. D. Modern Approaches for Asymmetric Construction of Carbon-Fluorine Quaternary Stereogenic Centers: Synthetic Challenges and Pharmaceutical Needs. *Chem. Rev.* 2018, 118, 3887.
- (4) For recent reviews on the Pauson-Khand reaction, see: (a) Ricker, J. D.; Geary, L. M. Recent Advances in the Pauson-Khand Reaction. *Top. Catal.* 2017, 60, 609. (b) *The Pauson Khand Reaction. Scope, Variations and Applications*; Ríos Torres, R., Ed; Wiley: Chichester, U.K., 2012. (c) Lee, H.; Kwong, F. A Decade of Advancements in Pauson-Khand-Type Reactions. *Eur. J. Org. Chem.* 2010, 2010, 789. (d) Park, J. H.; Chang, K.; Chung, Y. K. Catalytic Pauson-Khand-type reactions and related carbonylative cycloaddition reactions. *Coord. Chem. Rev.* 2009, 253, 2461. (e) Gibson, S. E.; Mainolfi, N. The intermolecular Pauson-Khand reaction. *Angew. Chem., Int. Ed.* 2005, 44, 3022. (f) Blanco-Urgoiti, J.; Anorbe, L.; Pérez-Serrano, L.; Domínguez, G.; Perez-Castells, J. The Pauson-Khand reaction, a powerful synthetic tool for the synthesis of complex molecules. *Chem. Soc. Rev.* 2004, 33, 32. (g) Pericaş M. A.; Balsells, J.; Castro, J.; Marchueta, I.; Moyano, A.; Riera, A.; Vázquez, J.; Verdaguier, X. Toward the understanding of the mechanism and enantioselectivity of the Pauson-Khand reaction. Theoretical and experimental studies. *Pure Appl. Chem.* 2002, 74, 167.
- (5) For a recent review on monofluorination, see: (a) Champagne, P. A.; Desroches, J.; Hamel, J.-D.; Vandamme, M.; Paquin, J.-F. Monofluorination of Organic Compounds: 10 Years of Innovation. *Chem. Rev.* 2015, 115, 9073. For a feature article on our own contributions in the field, see: (b) Fustero, S.; Sedgwick, D. M.; Román, R.; Barrio, P. Recent advances in the synthesis of functionalized monofluorinated compounds. *Chem. Commun.* 2018, 54, 9706.
- (6) For selected recent examples, see: (a) León, T.; Fernández, E. The Pauson-Khand reaction using alkynylboronic esters: solving a long-standing regioselectivity issue. *Chem. Commun.* 2016, 52, 9363. (b) Fustero, S.; Lázaro, R.; Aiguabella, N.; Riera, A.; Simon-Fuentes, A.; Barrio, P. Asymmetric Alkylation/Pauson-Khand Reaction: A Simple Entry to Polycyclic Amines. Application to the Synthesis of Aminosteroid Analogues. *Org. Lett.* 2014, 16, 1224. (c) Aiguabella, N.; del Pozo, C.; Verdaguier, X.; Fustero, S.; Riera, A. Synthesis and Application of β -Substituted Pauson-Khand Adducts: Trifluoromethyl as a Removable Steering Group. *Angew. Chem., Int. Ed.* 2013, 52, 5355.
- (7) For a somewhat obscure failed attempt, see: (a) Ishizaki, M.; Suzuki, D.; Hoshino, O. Scope and limitation of intramolecular Pauson-Khand reaction of fluorine-containing enynes. *J. Fluorine Chem.* 2001, 111, 81. For the only example of the use of a vinylsulfone in an intermolecular PKR, see: (b) Ahmar, M.; Antras, F.; Cazes, B. Pauson-Khand reaction of activated olefins. *Tetrahedron Lett.* 1999, 40, 5503.
- (8) Perhaps the closest precedent would be Ichikawa's work using a CF₃ substituent at the olefin; see: Nadano, R.; Fuchibe, K.; Ikeda, M.; Takahashi, H.; Ichikawa, J. Rapid and Slow Generation of 1-Trifluoromethylvinyl lithium: Syntheses and Applications of CF₃-Containing Allylic Alcohols, Allylic Amines, and Vinyl Ketones. *Chem. - Asian J.* 2010, 5, 1875.
- (9) Liang, T.; Neumann, C.; Ritter, T. Introduction of Fluorine and Fluorine-Containing Functional Groups. *Angew. Chem., Int. Ed.* 2013, 52, 8214.
- (10) The most closely related example found was the corresponding terminal gem-difluoro derivative described by Chatani and co-workers; see: Takachi, M.; Kita, Y.; Tobisu, M.; Fukumoto, Y.; Chatani, N. Nickel-catalyzed cyclization of difluoro-substituted 1,6-enynes with organozinc reagents through the stereoselective activation of C-F bonds: synthesis of bicyclo[3.2.0]heptene derivatives. *Angew. Chem., Int. Ed.* 2010, 49, 8717.
- (11) Okoromoba, O. E.; Han, J.; Hammond, G. B.; Xu, B. Designer HF-Based Fluorination Reagent: Highly Regioselective Synthesis of Fluoroalkenes and gem-Difluoromethylene Compounds from Alkynes. *J. Am. Chem. Soc.* 2014, 136, 14381.
- (12) (a) Rodríguez, E.; Grayson, M. N.; Asensio, A.; Barrio, P.; Houk, K. N.; Fustero, S. Chiral Brønsted Acid-Catalyzed Asymmetric Allyl(propargyl)boration Reaction of *ortho*-Alkynyl Benzaldehydes: Synthetic Applications and Factors Governing the Enantioselectivity. *ACS Catal.* 2016, 6, 2506. (b) Herrera, L.; Barrio, P.; Ibañez, I.; Román, R.; Mateu, N.; Fustero, S. 8-Iodonaphthalene-1-carbaldehyde: A Versatile Building Block for Diversity-Oriented Synthesis. *Org. Lett.* 2016, 18, 4722.
- (13) (a) Grigg, R.; Zhang, L.; Collard, S.; Keep, A. Palladium-catalyzed [2 + 2 + 1] intramolecular cycloaddition for the preparation of bicyclo[3.3.0]octa-1.5-dien-3-ones from 1,6-diyne. *Chem. Commun.* 2003, 1902. (b) Vorobyeva, D. V.; Mailyan, A. K.; Peregudov, A. S.; Karimova, N. M.; Vasilyeva, T. P.; Bushmarinov, I. S.; Bruneau, C.; Dixneuf, P. H.; Osipov, S. N. Synthesis of functionalized CF₃-containing heterocycles via [2,3]-sigmatropic rearrangement and sequential catalytic carbocyclization. *Tetrahedron* 2011, 67, 3524.
- (14) Control experiments confirmed that 3a was recovered unaltered after being stirred overnight in the presence of 10 equiv of *N*-methylmorpholine (NMM) in DCM overnight. Moreover, treatment of 5a with NMM under the same reaction conditions resulted in its clean transformation to 4a.
- (15) Chung, Y.; Lee, B.; Jeong, N.; Hudecek, M.; Pauson, P. Promoters for the (alkyne) hexacarbonyldicobalt-based cyclopentene synthesis. *Organometallics* 1993, 12, 220.
- (16) Zhan, Z.-p.; Yu, J. l.; Liu, H.-j.; Cui, Y.-y.; Yang, R.-f.; Yang, W.-z.; Li, J.-p. A General and Efficient FeCl₃-Catalyzed Nucleophilic Substitution of Propargylic Alcohols. *J. Org. Chem.* 2006, 71, 8298.
- (17) Tkachenko, A. N.; Radchenko, D. S.; Mykhailiuk, P. K.; Grygorenko, O. O.; Komarov, I. V. 4-Fluoro-2,4-methanoproline. *Org. Lett.* 2009, 11, 5674.
- (18) For reviews on the pharmacologic activity of isatin derivatives, see: (a) Vine, K. I.; Matesic, I.; Locke, J. M.; Skropeta, D. Recent highlights in the development of isatin-based anticancer agents. *Adv. Anticancer Agents Med. Chem.* 2013, 2, 254. (b) Vine, K. I.; Matesic, I.; Locke, J. M.; Ranson, M.; Skropeta, D. Cytotoxic and anticancer activities of isatin and its derivatives: a comprehensive review from 2000–2008. *Anti-Cancer Agents Med. Chem.* 2009, 9, 397.
- (19) The reaction with the corresponding non-fluorinated analog is reported to proceed in 80% yield under NMO-promoted reaction conditions; see: Jeong, N.; Chung, Y. K.; Lee, B. Y.; Lee, S.; Yoo, S.-E. A Dramatic Acceleration of the Pauson-Khand Reaction by Trimethylamine *N*-Oxide. *Synlett* 1991, 1991, 204.
- (20) Druzhenko, T.; Denisenko, O.; Kheylk, Y.; Zozulya, S.; Shishkina, S. S.; Tolmachev, A.; Mykhailiuk, P. K. Design, Synthesis, and Characterization of SO₂-Containing Azabicyclo[3.n.1]alkanes: Promising Building Blocks for Drug Discovery. *Org. Lett.* 2015, 17, 1922.
- (21) The stereochemistry of the products 5k and 5q was established by means of 2D-NMR HOESY experiments. The stereochemistry of 5r was tentatively assigned by analogy to 5q.
- (22) For selected recent examples, see: (a) Liu, X.-G.; Zhou, C.-J.; Lin, E.; Han, X.-L.; Zhang, S.-S.; Li, Q.; Wang, H. Decarboxylative Negishi Coupling of Redox-Active Aliphatic Esters by Cobalt Catalysis. *Angew. Chem., Int. Ed.* 2018, 57, 13096. (b) Xue, W.; Shishido, R.; Oestreich, M. Bench-Stable Stock Solutions of Silicon Grignard Reagents: Application to Iron- and Cobalt-Catalyzed Radical C(sp³)-Si

Cross-Coupling Reactions. *Angew. Chem., Int. Ed.* 2018, 57, 12141.

(23) For a recent report on the asymmetric synthesis of regioisomeric α -fluorocyclopentenones by means of a tandem Nazarov cyclization/electrophilic fluorination sequence, see: Zhang, H.; Cheng, B.; Lu, Z. Enantioselective Cobalt-Catalyzed Sequential Nazarov Cyclization/Electrophilic Fluorination: Access to Chiral α -Fluorocyclopentenones. *Org. Lett.* 2018, 20, 4028.

(24) For recent examples of the catalytic enantioselective PKR, see:

(a) Garcon, M.; Cabre, A.; Verdaguer, X.; Riera, A. Synthesis, Coordination Study, and Catalytic Pauson-Khand Reactions of QuinoxP*(CO)₄- μ -Alkyne Dicobalt Complexes. *Organometallics* 2017, 36, 1056. (b) Cristobal-Lecina, E.; Costantino, A. R.; Grabulosa, A.; Riera, A.; Verdaguer, X. Rhodium-Catalyzed Pauson-Khand Reaction Using a Small-Bite-Angle P-Stereogenic C1-Diphosphine Ligand. *Organometallics* 2015, 34, 4989. For seminal contributions, see: (c) Jeong, N.; Sung, B. K.; Choi, Y. K. Rhodium(I)-Catalyzed Asymmetric Intramolecular Pauson-Khand-Type Reaction. *J. Am. Chem. Soc.* 2000, 122, 6771. (d) Shibata, T.; Takagi, K. Iridium-Chiral Diphosphine Complex Catalyzed Highly Enantioselective Pauson-Khand-Type Reaction. *J. Am. Chem. Soc.* 2000, 122, 9852.

(25) For selected recent applications of 1,6-enynes, see: (a) Wang, C.; Ge, S. Versatile Cobalt-Catalyzed Enantioselective Entry to Boryl-Functionalized All-Carbon Quaternary Stereogenic Centers. *J. Am. Chem. Soc.* 2018, 140, 10687. (b) Li, M.; Wang, C.-T.; Qiu, Y.-F.; Zhu, X.-Y.; Han, Y.-P.; Xia, Y.; Li, X.-S.; Liang, Y.-M. Base promoted

direct difunctionalization/cascade cyclization of 1,6-enynes. *Chem. Commun.* 2018, 54, 5334. (c) Cao, X.; Cheng, X.; Xuan, J. Arylsulfonyl Radical Triggered 1,6-Enyne Cyclization: Synthesis of γ -Lactams Containing Alkenyl C-X Bonds. *Org. Lett.* 2018, 20, 449. For selected recent reviews on transition-metal-catalyzed reactions using enynes as substrates, see: (d) Harris, R. J.; Widenhoefer, R. A. Gold carbenes, gold-stabilized carbocations, and cationic intermediates relevant to gold-catalyzed enyne cycloaddition. *Chem. Soc. Rev.* 2016, 45, 4533. (e) Dorel, R.; Echavarren, A. M. Gold-Catalyzed Reactions via Cyclopropyl Gold Carbene-like Intermediates. *J. Org. Chem.* 2015, 80, 7321.